

Clinicomycological Study of Onychomycosis In Dermatology Patients Attending A Tertiary Care Hospital.

First Author- Dr. Sharvari A. Samant¹

Professor

Department of Microbiology

MGM Medical College and Hospital, Kamothe, Navi Mumbai,
Maharashtra, India.

Second Author- Parnika Patil²

M.Sc. Medical Microbiology Resident

Department of Microbiology

MGM Medical College and Hospital, Kamothe, Navi Mumbai,
Maharashtra, India.

Third Author & Corresponding Author - Aishwarya D. Warang*

Tutor.

Department of Microbiology

MGM Medical College and Hospital, Kamothe, Navi Mumbai,
Maharashtra, India.

Fourth Author- Dr. Shylaja Someshwar⁴

Professor and HOD.

Department of Dermatology and VL,

Adjunct Professor, Department of Dermatology and VL, Kasturba Medical
College (KMC), MAHE, Mangalore.

Department of Dermatology and VL, MGM Medical College and Hospital, Kamothe,
Navi Mumbai.

ABSTRACT

Background: Onychomycosis is a fungal infection of the nail unit—comprising the nail plate, nail bed, and surrounding tissues. It is a **chronic and progressive** condition and is the **most common disease of the nails**, accounting for about **50% of all nail disorders**. While not life-threatening, it can cause **significant morbidity** due to discomfort, pain, and cosmetic concerns, and it may also serve as a reservoir for fungal infections in other parts of the body, particularly in immunocompromised individuals.

Aim: To study and evaluate the clinico-mycological pattern of onychomycosis in patients attending to Tertiary Care Hospital in Navi Mumbai.

Methods: A total of 118 nail specimens were obtained from individuals suspected of having onychomycosis. Severely affected nail clippings were examined using potassium hydroxide (KOH) mounts for direct microscopy and cultured on Sabouraud's dextrose agar and Dermatophyte Test Medium to aid in fungal identification.

Results: Out of the 118 cultured nail specimens, 50 fungal organisms were isolated. The majority of affected patients were aged between 46 and 55 years, with a higher prevalence of onychomycosis observed in males compared to females. Distal and lateral subungual onychomycosis was the most common clinical type, seen in 42% of the cases. Among patients with onychomycosis, diabetes mellitus and hypertension were the predominant co-morbid conditions. Dermatophytes were identified in 58% of the cases, while 24% showed growth of non-dermatophyte fungi. The main pathogens isolated included *Trichophyton rubrum*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Candida albicans*, and *Aspergillus niger*, which were responsible for the infections.

Limitations: Treatment and further follow up of patients was not done due to time constraint

Conclusion: Accurate identification of the cause of onychomycosis is essential for effective treatment and improved quality of life. While not a major public health risk, early diagnosis supports timely therapy, nail recovery, and prevents complications or recurrence.

Keywords: Onychomycosis, Dermatophytes, *Trichophyton*

Introduction

Previously referred to specifically as a non-dermatophytic nail infection, the term onychomycosis is now broadly used to describe any fungal infection of the nails. Dermatophytic infection of the nail are referred to as Tineaungium. The term encompasses all fungal infections involving the nail apparatus, including the nail plate, nail matrix, cuticle, surrounding mesenchymal tissue, and nail folds. Onychomycosis accounts for up to 50% of nail-related disorders and approximately 30% of all superficial fungal infections affecting the nails.⁽¹⁾

In accordance with the clinical condition and the identified invasion route, onychomycosis is divided into four categories: Proximal subungual nail infection, candidal nail infection, white superficial nail infection, and distal subungual nail infection. Aging, nail injuries, decreased peripheral circulation, psoriasis, history of athlete's foot, unsanitary nail conditions, and sweating are some of the factors associated with an increased risk of infection. Even though it is not fatal, onychomycosis can end up causing secondary infections leading to symptomatic disease which can be a cause of morbidity with a negative impact such as pain and can potentially sabotage social lives.⁽²⁾ Due to inadequate medical facilities in especially

rural areas, onychomycosis is considered as a persistent fungal infection leading to increasing morbidities. It is necessary to understand the pathogenesis and etiology in order to treat the recurrence of infection. The aim of the present study was to examine the various fungal agents responsible for causing onychomycosis in patients.

MATERIALS & METHODS

This study was conducted over a two-year period, from December 2021 to February 2023, in the Department of Microbiology at MGM Medical College and Hospital, Kamothe, Navi, Mumbai. A total of 50 organisms were isolated from 118 clinically suspected nail specimens.

All the samples were processed as per the standard microbiological guidelines⁽³⁾

1. Microscopy

- a) KOH Mount -: The nail samples were subjected to KOH mount for preliminary identification of the kind of fungal infection by dissolving the keratinized nail samples and detection of refractile hyphae.
- b) Gram's Staining: The samples were also subjected to Gram's staining for identification of budding yeast cells with or without Pseudohyphae.

2. Culture on SDA and DTM: The nail specimens were subsequently cultured on Sabouraud's Dextrose Agar and Dermatophyte Test Medium, incubated at 25°C and 37°C. They were examined daily during the first week and then twice a week for a duration of 6 weeks, with colony characteristics being monitored for organism identification.

3. Slide Culture: For classifying different types of fungi based on the colony morphology (obverse and reverse).

4. Species Identification:

- a) Urea Hydrolysis Test – For identification of *Trichophytonmentagrophytes*.

b) Germ Tube Test and CHROM agar – To differentiate between *Candida* species.

RESULT

A total of 118 patients were assessed in this study, with nail samples from 50 patients showing fungal growth. The largest group of patients affected by onychomycosis was in the 46–55 age range, comprising 15 patients (30%), followed by 11 patients (22%) in the 56–65 age group. Males (66%) were more affected than females (34%) with a ratio of 2.2:1. When the history of patients with onychomycosis was analyzed, it was observed that prolonged contact with water and wearing tight footwear could be the predisposing factors. Also, it was observed that amongst males, the labourers were most affected by onychomycosis than the ones with any other occupation. Amongst females, housewives were most affected as compared to other working females. Onychomycosis patients when questioned about any other co-morbidities, it was observed that Diabetes mellitus (18%) was the most frequently associated condition, followed by hypertension (12%) and thyroid. Percentage distribution of growth observed in cases of Onychomycosis. (n=50). (Figure 1)

Dermatophytes were found to be the predominant cause of onychomycosis, with a prevalence rate of 58% followed by Non-dermatophyte mold 24% (Figure 2). The Age-Wise Distribution Percentage of Patients with Onychomycosis.(n=50). In our study, the majority of patients affected by onychomycosis were in the 46–55 age group, accounting for 15 patients (30%), while the least affected were in the 76–85 age group, with only 2% of cases. Gender Distribution of patients with Onychomycosis. (n=50). Males (66%) were more than females (34%) with a ratio of 2.2:1.(Figure 3)

Figure 1. Percentage Distribution of Growth Observed in Cases of Onychomycosis. (n=50).

Figure 2. Age-Wise Distribution of Patients with Onychomycosis. (n=50)

Figure 3. Gender Distribution of patients with Onychomycosis. (n=50)**Table 1. Percentage of Onychomycosis patients showing various clinical symptoms.**

Complaints	No. of Patients	Percentage
A. Onycholysis	11	22%
B. Paronychia	8	16%
C. Brown-black Discoloration	25	50%
D. Yellowish Discoloration	19	38%
E. White Discoloration (Leukonychia)	8	16%
F. Loss of Cuticle	3	6%
G. Dystrophic Nail	6	12%
H. Ridges	4	8%

The predominant nail changes observed were discoloration, among which brownish-black (50%) and yellow discoloration (38.5%) were the most common observations whereas loss of cuticle and history of discharge were seen with least rate of 6%.

Table 2. Isolates Found in Onychomycosis Cases. (n=50)

No.	Organism	No. of Isolates	Percentage of Isolates
1.	<i>Trichophyton rubrum</i>	21	42%
2.	<i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i>	8	16%
3.	<i>Aspergillusniger</i>	12	24%
4.	<i>Candida albicans</i>	9	18%

Trichophytonrubrum (42%) was the most commonly isolated organism responsible for onychomycosis, followed by *Aspergillusniger* at 24%. *Trichophytonmentagrophytes* was the least frequently isolated organism.

Table 3. Spectrum of Organisms Isolated in Various Clinical Types.

Organism isolated Clinical Type ↓	<i>Trichophytonrubrum</i>	<i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>	<i>Aspergillusniger</i>
Distal and Lateral Subungual Onychomycosis (DLSO)	13(26%)	-	-	8(16%)
Proximal Subungual Onychomycosis (PSO)	8(16%)	-	-	4(8%)

White Superficial Onychomycosis (WSO)	-	8(16%)	-	-
Candidal Onychomycosis (CO)	-	-	9(18%)	-

Distal and Lateral Subungual Onychomycosis (DLSO) was the most prevalent clinical presentation, occurring in 21 patients (42%), with *T. rubrum* and *A. niger* identified as the primary causative organisms, followed by Proximal Subungual Onychomycosis (PSO) in 12(24%) patients caused by the similar organisms as DLSO. Candidal onychomycosis (CO) was seen next in frequency with 9 (18%) patients. CO was observed as paronychia in five (55.5%) patients and nail plate discoloration in two (22.2%) of these patients with *C. albicans* as the agent responsible. White Superficial Onychomycosis (WSO) was the least common type, observed in only eight (16%) patients majorly caused by *T. mentagrophytes*.

Distribution of Onychomycosis patients with associated co-morbidities. Patients with Diabetes mellitus (36%) and Hypertension (24%) were more prone to onychomycosis.

(Figure 4)

Figure 4. Co-morbidity Distribution in Patients Diagnosed with Onychomycosis.

DISCUSSION

Onychomycosis is a persistent fungal infection of the fingernails and toenails that significantly affects the quality of life. Onychomycosis was common since ages but has been diagnosed more commonly now. This has shown high prevalence nowadays. The current study aimed to assess the microbial profile of clinically suspected onychomycosis cases, considering various factors that influence the disease.

In our study, the rate of microbial isolation in onychomycosis was determined to be 42.3%. In a similar study, Rupali S. Suryawanshi *et al.*⁽⁴⁾ from Mumbai have reported the microbial isolation rate 58.41%. Eleonora Dubljanin *et al.*⁽⁵⁾ *et al.*, conducted a study on Epidemiology of Onychomycosis in Serbia that included 374 patients out of which diagnosis of onychomycosis was confirmed by culture in 50.8% of them. This indicates that the prevalence of onychomycosis was less in one area which is a semi-rural area.

It was observed that a large number of the patients were affected with onychomycosis were in the age group of 46–55 (Figure 2). Similar findings were reported by Nourchene Toukabriet *et al.*

⁽⁶⁾ who studied about 392 patients and the most infected patients were in the age group of 41-50 followed by those between 51-60. In our study, the majority of nails affected were fingernails with a rate of 66%. Toenails were affected in 17(34%) patients. Our study aligned with a study from Uttarakhand in India by Adekhandi S, *et.al*⁽⁷⁾, however study of Gupta M *et.al*⁽⁸⁾ from Himachal Pradesh have reported that toenails were more frequently affected than fingernail. This shows that prevalence of onychomycosis varies from place to place which may be governed by the temperature, humidity in particular area.

The predominant nail changes observed in our study are depicted in Table 1 among which brownish-black (50%) and yellow discoloration (38%) were the major symptoms whereas onycholysis turned out to be the second most observed nail deformity in 11 (25%) patients. Study done by Kaur R *et al*⁽⁹⁾ showed similar results where Discoloration was the most frequently observed symptom. Findings by Reddy KN *et.al*⁽¹⁰⁾ revealed 100% i.e 60/60 patients were seen with discoloration of nails as the common clinical presentation.

In this study the predisposing factors of onychomycosis were checked. It was observed that patients with a history of prolonged contact with water were identified as the most significant cause followed by history of wearing tight footwear accounted for 29% of the infection. Similar results were presented by SenA *et.al*⁽¹¹⁾ in a study done in Eastern Bihar with exposure to water as a common factor. More exposure to water makes a suitable condition for fungi to grow and infect the nails. This can be avoided by guiding the patients to keep the nails dry after exposure to water.

The correlation of occupation with the cases of onychomycosis was studied. It was observed that majority of sufferers amongst males were labourers (27%) and servicemen (18%) followed by farmers at a rate of 13% and Drivers (7%). Amongst Females, housewives (18%) were found to have more chances of having onychomycosis. Study done by Reddy KN *et.al*

⁽¹⁰⁾ shows that amongst 60 patients, housewives were in majority at a rate of 26.6% followed by laborers (16.6%) which is similar to our study. In contrast the study done by Gupta M *et.al* ⁽⁸⁾ has reported that farmers were majorly affected by onychomycosis. This could be attributed to the basic hygiene level of an individual.

The associated comorbidities with onychomycosis found in this study are depicted in Figure 4 which shows majority of the patients were being treated for diabetes (36%) and hypertension (25%). Arenas R *et.al* ⁽¹²⁾ conducted a survey in Mexico which presented diabetes mellitus and arterial hypertension as the major underlying comorbidity in patients suffering from onychomycosis. Both the studies done by Elewski BE *et.al* ⁽¹³⁾ and Papini M *et.al* ⁽¹⁴⁾ reveals that patients with diabetes are more prone to the disease. This shows that the patients having diabetes mellitus & hypertension should take care of nails as they are more prone to onychomycosis.

Table 2 shows Isolates found in onychomycosis cases in our study. In our study, dermatophytes were the primary cause of onychomycosis cases. *T. rubrum* was the most prevalent dermatophyte responsible for Distal and Lateral Subungual Onychomycosis (DLSO) in 23% of patients and Proximal Subungual Onychomycosis (PSO) in 18% of cases. *T. mentagrophytes*, found in 20% of cases, was the second most common dermatophyte identified. Additionally, *C. albicans* was the most frequently isolated yeast, present in 16% of the samples. Isolation of Non-dermatophyte molds is seen in 25% of the cases. *Aspergillus niger* was isolated amongst 25% of all cases. It showed the symptoms of DLSO in 18% of the cases and PSO in 7% cases. Study done within Canadian Population by RB Vender *et.al* ⁽¹⁵⁾ reveals dermatophytes as the most commonly cultured organism which appeared in 71-91% of nails. In contrast, a study by M. Soltani *et al.* ⁽¹⁶⁾ conducted in Iran on onychomycosis in 140 patients visiting the dermatology department found that 79 patients

tested positive for onychomycosis. Yeasts were the most frequently isolated pathogens, accounting for 71.4%, followed by non-dermatophytic molds in 17.1% of cases. Dermatophytes were the least commonly isolated organisms, found in only 11.5% of patients. Table 3 shows the spectrum of organism in various clinical types. In the present study, Distal and Lateral Subungual Onychomycosis (DLSO) was the most common clinical presentation seen in 21 (42%) patients in which *T. rubrum* (26%) & *Aspergillus niger* (16%) were grown followed by Proximal Subungual Onychomycosis (PSO) in 12 (24%) patients in which *T. rubrum* was isolated in 16% patients & *Aspergillus niger* in 8% patients. Candidal Onychomycosis (CO) was observed as paronychia in five (37.5%) patients and nail plate discoloration in two (25%) of these patients and was observed next in frequency in 16% patients. White Superficial Onychomycosis (WSO) was the most infrequent form with 8 (16%) patients with *T. mentagrophytes* (16%) as major isolates. A Study done in North East India by Marak A et.al⁽¹⁷⁾ 68 out of 80 were affected by onychomycosis. The majority of which was clinically presented as DLSO at a high rate of 73.52%, similar to our study. However the study conducted by TMJesudanam⁽¹⁸⁾ et al indicates Candidal Onychomycosis (CO) with high isolation rate. Proximal Subungual Onychomycosis (PSO) was the next clinical type found in majority of patients as seen in studies from Uttarakhand and Bangalore which were found similar to our study. The least common clinical type was White Superficial Onychomycosis (WSO) with similar results from the study done by Reddy KN.⁽¹⁹⁾ The spectrum of fungi varies in different geographic areas.

CONCLUSION

Hence baseline studies can be performed in different geographic areas to know the common etiological agents of onychomycosis in those areas for which the empiric treatment can be standardized. Even though onychomycosis does not pose a severe public health issue,

determination of etiological of the disease is crucial to enhance quality of life. Additionally, raising awareness of the disease is essential since, especially in rural areas, people tend to ignore the issue, which has further adverse impacts. A proper diagnosis will eventually help in reaching the desired outcome, which is total recovery and restoration of the damaged nails.

REFERENCES

1. Jaiswal A, Sharma RP, Gupta K. Onychomycosis: A clinicomycological study from western Uttar Pradesh, India. *Indian Journal of Medical Specialities*. 2015;6(1):8-12.
2. Ahuja S, Malhotra S, Charoo H. Etiological agents of onychomycosis from a tertiary care hospital in Central Delhi, India. *Indian J Fundamental and Appl Life Sci*. 2011;1:11-4.
3. Winn W, Allen S, Janda W, Koneman E, Procop G, Schreckenberger P, Woods G. *Color Atlas and Textbook of Diagnostic Microbiology*. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins;2006.
4. Suryawanshi RS, Wanjare SW, Koticha AH, Mehta PR. Onychomycosis: dermatophytes to yeasts: an experience in and around Mumbai, Maharashtra, India. *Int J Res Med Sci*. 2017;5(5):1959-63.
5. Dubljanin E, Džamić A, Vujčić I, Grujičić SŠ, Arsenijević VA, Mitrović S, et al . Epidemiology of onychomycosis in Serbia: a laboratory-based survey and risk factor identification. *Mycoses*. 2017;60(1):25-32.
6. Toukabri N, Dhieb C, El Euch D, Rouissi M, Mokni M, Sadfi-Zouaoui N. Prevalence, etiology, and risk factors of tinea pedis and tinea unguium in Tunisia. *Canadian Journal of Infectious Diseases and Medical Microbiology*. 2017;2017(1):3.

7. Adekhandi S, Pal S, Sharma N, Juyal D, Sharma M, Dimri D. Incidence and epidemiology of onychomycosis in patients visiting a tertiary care hospital in India. *Cutis*. 2015;95(1):20-25.
8. Gupta M, Sharma NL, Kanga AK, Mahajan VK, Tegta GR. Onychomycosis: Clinico-mycologic study of 130 patients from Himachal Pradesh, India. *Indian Journal of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprology*. 2007;73:389.
9. Kaur R, Kashyap B, Bhalla P. A five-year survey of onychomycosis in New Delhi, India: Epidemiological and laboratory aspects. *Indian Journal of Dermatology*. 2007;52(1):39-42.
10. Reddy KN, Srikanth BA, Sharan TR, Biradar PM. Epidemiological, clinical and cultural study of onychomycosis. *Am J Dermatol Venereol*.2012;1(3):35-40.
11. Sen A, Bhunia D, Datta PK, Ray A, Banerjee P. A study of onychomycosis at a tertiary care hospital in Eastern Bihar. *Indian Journal of Dermatology*.2018;63(2):141-6.
12. Arenas R, Bonifaz A, Padilla MC, Arce M, Atoche C, Barba J, Campos P, Fernández R, Mayorga J, Nazar D, Ocampo J. Onychomycosis. A Mexican survey. *European Journal of Dermatology*.2010;20(5):611-4.
13. Elewski BE. Onychomycosis: pathogenesis, diagnosis, and management. *Clinical microbiology reviews*.1998;11(3):415-29.
14. Papini M, Piraccini BM, Difonzo E, Brunoro A. Epidemiology of onychomycosis in Italy: prevalence data and risk factor identification. *Mycoses*.2015;58(11):659-64.
15. Vender RB, Lynde CW, Poulin Y. Prevalence and epidemiology of onychomycosis. *Journal of cutaneous medicine and surgery*.2006;10(6):28-33.

16. Soltani M, Khosravi AR, Shokri H, Sharifzadeh A, Balal A. A study of onychomycosis in patients attending a dermatology center in Tehran, Iran. *Journal de mycologiemedicale*. 2015;25(2):81-7.
17. Marak A, Verma S, Lyngdoh WV, Dey B. Dermatoscopic Features of Onychomycosis and its Correlation with Nail Plate Potassium Hydroxide Mount(KOH), Culture, and Periodic Acid Schiff Stain (PAS) in North East India. *Indian J Dermatol*. 2021 ;66(6):625-631.
18. Jesudanam TM, Rao GR, Lakshmi DJ, Kumari GR. Onychomycosis: A significant medical problem. *Indian Journal of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprology*. 2002Nov; 68:326.
19. Reddy KN, Srikanth BA, Sharan TR, Biradar PM. Epidemiological, clinical and cultural study of onychomycosis. *Am J Dermatol Venereol*. 2012;1(3):35-40.